

Document information	
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Authors	Björn Haßler, Taskeen Adam, Meaghan Brugha, Kalifa Damani, Zoe Allier-Gagneur, Sara Hennessy, David Hollow, Katy Jordan, Nasia Kotsiou, Kevin Martin, Nora McIntyre, Mary Murphy, Kristi Nourie, Hannah Walker
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USER GUIDE					
<p>Purpose: This sheet serves as a database of search terms for the systematic literature review in Q1 of the EdTech Hub. Terms have been presented in separate tabs that group terms categorically. These are explained in the table below. Each term is also given an ID number, a batch code, a category and sub-category, as well as a semantic value and unique code. The term is then translated from English into the other searched languages.</p>					
<p>ID number and priority ranking: Priority columns identify whether the term will be included in both automated and manual search (H), solely an automated search (M), or tagged and not searched for (L).</p>					
<p>Categories and sub-categories: The tabs are split into the overall categories of keywords and are expanded on in the table below. Within the separate categories, keywords are further categorised into relevant subcategories as a way to further disaggregate the literature base, following the completion of the review.</p>					
<p>Semantic value and unique codes: Each term is given both a semantic value and a unique code. Often this will be the same as the English translation, but some terms will have multiple variations, abbreviations, etc. and will therefore have the same semantic value.</p>					
<p>Translations: These search terms were consistently translated (at times manually and at times automatically) into the 5 UN languages other than English: French, Russian, Chinese, Spanish, Arabic. Search terms were also translated into Portuguese.</p>					
Category	Short code	Description	Batch	Sub-categories	Additional information
Countries / areas	GC	These terms are names of the countries and areas that fit within the research criteria. For full dataset of countries, including formula for inclusion see the separate country list sheet: https://docs.edtechhub.org/lib/3BG5X7VG	H & M	area	
				country	
Regions	GR	These terms are names of continents and regions that fit within the research criteria, and includes synonyms and abbreviations.	H & M	region	Note that not all countries in the regions included as key terms are relevant - publications will have to be screened further.
Development-related	GD	These are terms that are broadly synonymous with LMIC / developing countries	H & M	developing context	
				fragile and conflict context	
Technology	TT	These terms are generalist technology terms, and are not specific to education technology.	H & M	accessibility and inclusion	
				communication and social media	
				device	
				electronic resource	
				general ICT	
model of delivery					

				operating system	
				software	
Edtech	TE	These terms are specialist technology terms that directly relate to education technology.	H & M	device	
				electronic resource	
				general edtech	
				model of delivery	
				software	
Population	P1	This sheet includes terms relating to education levels.	H & M	early childhood education	
				government	
				primary and secondary education	
				teacher and school staff education	
Population needing additional specifiers	P2	This sheet includes terms related to the educational context - educational level and type - that will need to be run against specific population specifiers. See target specifiers in Row 'I'.	H & M	accessibility and inclusion	
				primary and secondary education	
				education in emergencies	
				informal education	
				government	
				subject	
				teacher and school staff education	
Organisations and initiatives	O	These terms include relevant tech and edtech initiatives, learning platforms and organisations, which will be used for tagging only and will not be searched for. This sheet has been populated through different sources centred around numbers of users, innovation and scalability.	L	initiative	
				learning platform	
				organisation	
Focus	F	These terms are the focus words of publications that will be used for tagging only, and not searched.	L	accessibility and inclusion	
				educational finance	
				learner attitudes and behaviours	
				management and delivery context	
				model of delivery	
				outcomes and impact	
Research methods	R	These are terms that relate to research designs and methods, which will be used for tagging and not searched for.	L	research design	
				research method	

Search string combinations				
GC + TT + P1				
GC + TT + P2				
GR + TT + P1				
GR + TT + P2				
GD + TT + P1				
GD + TT + P2				
GC + TE				
GR + TE				
GD + TE				

Keyword category "GC": countries and disputed territories								
id	priority	entry type	Category			Code		Lexemes
			category	short	sub-category	semantic value	unique code	English
1	M	N=primary	geography	GC	area	Abkhazia	Abkhazia	Abkhazia
2	M	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Afghanistan	Afghanistan	Afghanistan
3	L	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Albania	Albania	Albania
4	M	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Algeria	Algeria	Algeria
5	L	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Andorra	Andorra	Andorra
6	M	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Angola	Angola	Angola
7	L	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Antigua and Barbuda	Antigua and Barbuda	Antigua and Barbuda
8	L	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Argentina	Argentina	Argentina
9	M	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Armenia	Armenia	Armenia
10	M	N=primary	geography	GC	area	Artsakh	Artsakh	Artsakh
11	M	N=variation	geography	GC	area	Artsakh	Nagorno-Karabakh	Nagorno-Karabakh
12	L	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Australia	Australia	Australia
13	L	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Austria	Austria	Austria
14	M	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Azerbaijan	Azerbaijan	Azerbaijan
15	L	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Bahamas	Bahamas	Bahamas
16	L	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Bahrain	Bahrain	Bahrain
17	H	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Bangladesh	Bangladesh	Bangladesh
18	L	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Barbados	Barbados	Barbados
19	L	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Belarus	Belarus	Belarus
20	L	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Belgium	Belgium	Belgium
21	M	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Belize	Belize	Belize
22	M	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Benin	Benin	Benin
23	M	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Bhutan	Bhutan	Bhutan
24	M	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Bolivia	Bolivia	Bolivia
25	M	N=variation	geography	GC	country	Bolivia	Plurinational State of Bolivia	Plurinational State of Bolivia
26	M	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Bosnia and Herzegovina	Bosnia and Herzegovina	Bosnia and Herzegovina
27	M	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Botswana	Botswana	Botswana
28	M	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Brazil	Brazil	Brazil
29	L	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Brunei Darussalam	Brunei Darussalam	Brunei Darussalam

Keyword category "GC": countries and disputed territories								
id	priority	entry type	Category			Code		Lexemes
			category	short	sub-category	semantic value	unique code	English
30	L	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Bulgaria	Bulgaria	Bulgaria
31	H	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Burkina Faso	Burkina Faso	Burkina Faso
32	H	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Burundi	Burundi	Burundi
33	M	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Cambodia	Cambodia	Cambodia
34	M	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Cameroon	Cameroon	Cameroon
35	L	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Canada	Canada	Canada
37	M	N=variation	geography	GC	country	Cape Verde	Cabo Verde	Cabo Verde
36	M	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Cape Verde	Cape Verde	Cape Verde
38	L	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Catalan Republic	Catalan Republic	Catalan Republic
39	H	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Central African R	Central African Repub	Central African Republic
40	M	N=variation	geography	GC	country	Central African R	Central African Repub	Central African Republic
41	H	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Chad	Chad	Chad
42	L	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Chile	Chile	Chile
43	M	N=primary	geography	GC	country	China	China	China
44	M	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Colombia	Colombia	Colombia
45	H	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Comoros	Comoros	Comoros
47	M	N=variation	geography	GC	country	Congo	Congo	Congo
50	M	N=variation	geography	GC	country	Congo	Congo, Rep.	Congo, Rep.
51	M	N=variation (FR)	geography	GC	country	Congo	Republic of the Congo	Congo, Rep.
49	M	N=variation	geography	GC	country	Congo	Rep. of the Congo	Rep. of the Congo
46	M	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Congo	Republic of the Congo	Republic of the Congo
48	M	N=variation	geography	GC	country	Congo	Republic of the Congo	Republic of the Congo
52	M	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Costa Rica	Costa Rica	Costa Rica
54	M	N=variation	geography	GC	country	Côte d'Ivoire	Côte d'Ivoire	Côte d'Ivoire
53	M	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Côte d'Ivoire	Côte d'Ivoire	Ivory Coast
55	L	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Croatia	Croatia	Croatia
56	M	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Cuba	Cuba	Cuba
57	L	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Cyprus	Cyprus	Cyprus
58	L	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Czech Republic	Czech Republic	Czech Republic

Keyword category "GC": countries and disputed territories								
id	priority	entry type	Category			Code		Lexemes
			category	short	sub-category	semantic value	unique code	English
60	M	N=variation (FR)	geography	GC	country	Democratic Repu	CDR	Congo, Dem. Rep.
62	M	N=variation	geography	GC	country	Democratic Repu	Congo, Democratic Re	Congo, Democratic Republic of the
63	M	N=variation	geography	GC	country	Democratic Repu	Democratic Republic o	Dem. Rep. of the Congo
59	H	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Democratic Repu	Democratic Republic o	Democratic Republic of the Congo
61	M	N=variation	geography	GC	country	Democratic Repu	Democratic Republic o	Democratic Republic of the Congo
64	M	N=variation	geography	GC	country	Democratic Repu	DRC	DRC
65	L	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Denmark	Denmark	Denmark
66	M	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Djibouti	Djibouti	Djibouti
67	L	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Dominica	Dominica	Dominica
68	M	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Dominican Repu	Dominican Republic	Dominican Republic
69	M	N=variation (FR)	geography	GC	country	East Timor	East Timor	East Timor
70	M	N=variation (FR)	geography	GC	country	East Timor	Timor L'este	Timor L'este
71	M	N=primary	geography	GC	country	East Timor	Timor-Leste	Timor-L'este
72	M	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Ecuador	Ecuador	Ecuador
73	M	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Egypt	Egypt	Egypt
74	M	N=primary	geography	GC	country	El Salvador	El Salvador	El Salvador
75	M	N=variation (FR)	geography	GC	country	El Salvador	El Salvador	El Salvador
76	M	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Equatorial Guine	Equatorial Guinea	Equatorial Guinea
77	H	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Eritrea	Eritrea	Eritrea
78	L	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Estonia	Estonia	Estonia
79	M	N=primary	geography	GC	country	eSwatini	eSwatini	eSwatini
80	M	N=variation	geography	GC	country	eSwatini	Eswatini	Eswatini
81	M	N=variation	geography	GC	country	eSwatini	Kingdom of Eswatini	Kingdom of Eswatini
82	M	N=variation	geography	GC	country	eSwatini	Swaziland	Swaziland
83	M	N=variation (FR)	geography	GC	country	eSwatini	Swaziland	Swaziland
84	H	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Ethiopia	Ethiopia	Ethiopia
85	M	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Fiji	Fiji	Fiji
86	L	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Finland	Finland	Finland
87	L	N=primary	geography	GC	country	France	France	France

Keyword category "GC": countries and disputed territories								
id	priority	entry type	Category			Code		Lexemes
			category	short	sub-category	semantic value	unique code	English
88	M	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Gabon	Gabon	Gabon
89	H	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Gambia	Gambia	Gambia
91	M	N=variation	geography	GC	country	Gambia	Islamic republic of the	Islamic republic of the Gambia
90	M	N=variation	geography	GC	country	Gambia	Republic of the Gambi	Republic of the Gambia
92	M	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Georgia	Georgia	Georgia
93	L	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Germany	Germany	Germany
94	H	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Ghana	Ghana	Ghana
95	L	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Greece	Greece	Greece
96	L	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Grenada	Grenada	Grenada
97	M	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Guatemala	Guatemala	Guatemala
98	M	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Guinea	Guinea	Guinea
100	M	N=variation (FR)	geography	GC	country	Guinea-Bissau	Guinea-Bissau	Guinea
99	H	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Guinea-Bissau	Guinea-Bissau	Guinea-Bissau
101	M	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Guyana	Guyana	Guyana
102	M	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Haiti	Haiti	Haiti
103	M	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Honduras	Honduras	Honduras
104	L	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Hungary	Hungary	Hungary
105	L	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Iceland	Iceland	Iceland
106	H	N=primary	geography	GC	country	India	India	India
107	M	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Indonesia	Indonesia	Indonesia
108	L	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Iran (Islamic Rep	Iran (Islamic Republic	Iran (Islamic Republic of)
109	M	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Iraq	Iraq	Iraq
110	M	N=variation (FR)	geography	GC	country	Iraq	Iraq	Iraq
111	L	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Ireland	Ireland	Ireland
112	L	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Israel	Israel	Israel
113	L	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Italy	Italy	Italy
114	M	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Jamaica	Jamaica	Jamaica
115	L	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Japan	Japan	Japan
116	H	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Jordan	Jordan	Jordan

Keyword category "GC": countries and disputed territories								
id	priority	entry type	Category			Code		Lexemes
			category	short	sub-category	semantic value	unique code	English
117	L	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Kazakhstan	Kazakhstan	Kazakhstan
118	H	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Kenya	Kenya	Kenya
119	M	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Kiribati	Kiribati	Kiribati
120	L	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Korea (Republic	Korea (Republic of)	Korea (Republic of)
121	L	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Kosovo	Kosovo	Kosovo
122	M	N=primary	geography	GC	area	Kurdistan	Kurdistan	Kurdistan
123	L	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Kuwait	Kuwait	Kuwait
124	M	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Kyrgyzstan	Kyrgyzstan	Kyrgyzstan
125	M	N=variation (FR)	geography	GC	country	Kyrgyzstan	Kyrgyzstan	Kyrgyzstan
126	M	N=variation (FR)	geography	GC	country	Kyrgyzstan	Kyrgyzstan	Kyrgyzstan
127	M	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Laos	Laos	Laos
128	M	N=variation	geography	GC	country	Laos	Lao People's Democra	Laos People's Democratic Republic
129	L	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Latvia	Latvia	Latvia
130	H	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Lebanon	Lebanon	Lebanon
131	M	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Lesotho	Lesotho	Lesotho
132	H	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Liberia	Liberia	Liberia
133	M	N=variation (FR)	geography	GC	country	Liberia	Liberia	Liberia
134	M	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Libya	Libya	Libya
135	L	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Liechtenstein	Liechtenstein	Liechtenstein
136	L	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Lithuania	Lithuania	Lithuania
137	L	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Luxembourg	Luxembourg	Luxembourg
138	M	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Madagascar	Madagascar	Madagascar
139	H	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Malawi	Malawi	Malawi
140	L	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Malaysia	Malaysia	Malaysia
141	M	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Maldives	Maldives	Maldives
142	M	N=variation (FR)	geography	GC	country	Maldives	Maldives	Maldives
143	H	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Mali	Mali	Mali
144	L	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Malta	Malta	Malta
145	L	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Marshall Islands	Marshall Islands	Marshall Islands

Keyword category "GC": countries and disputed territories								
id	priority	entry type	Category			Code		Lexemes
			category	short	sub-category	semantic value	unique code	English
146	M	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Mauritania	Mauritania	Mauritania
147	M	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Mauritius	Mauritius	Mauritius
148	M	N=variation (FR)	geography	GC	country	Mauritius	Mauritius	Mauritius
149	M	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Mexico	Mexico	Mexico
150	M	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Micronesia	Federated States of M	Federated States of Micronesia
151	M	N=variation	geography	GC	country	Micronesia	Micronesia	Micronesia
153	M	N=variation	geography	GC	country	Moldova	Moldova	Moldova
152	M	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Moldova	Republic of Moldova	Republic of Moldova
154	L	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Monaco	Monaco	Monaco
155	M	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Mongolia	Mongolia	Mongolia
156	L	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Montenegro	Montenegro	Montenegro
157	M	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Morocco	Morocco	Morocco
158	H	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Mozambique	Mozambique	Mozambique
160	M	N=variation	geography	GC	country	Myanmar	Burma	Burma
159	M	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Myanmar	Myanmar	Myanmar
161	M	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Namibia	Namibia	Namibia
162	M	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Nauru	Nauru	Nauru
163	M	N=variation	geography	GC	country	Nauru	Nauru	Nauru
164	H	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Nepal	Nepal	Nepal
165	L	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Netherlands	Netherlands	Netherlands
167	L	N=variation	geography	GC	country	New Zealand	Aotearoa	Aotearoa
166	L	N=primary	geography	GC	country	New Zealand	New Zealand	New Zealand
168	M	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Nicaragua	Nicaragua	Nicaragua
169	H	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Niger	Niger	Niger
170	H	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Nigeria	Nigeria	Nigeria
171	L	N=primary	geography	GC	country	North Cyprus	North Cyprus	North Cyprus
172	M	N=primary	geography	GC	country	North Korea	North Korea	North Korea
173	M	N=primary	geography	GC	country	North Macedonia	North Macedonia	North Macedonia
176	M	N=variation	geography	GC	country	North Macedonia	Rep. of Macedonia	Rep. of Macedonia

Keyword category "GC": countries and disputed territories								
id	priority	entry type	Category			Code		Lexemes
			category	short	sub-category	semantic value	unique code	English
175	M	N=variation	geography	GC	country	North Macedonia	Republic of North Mac	Republic of North Macedonia
174	M	N=variation	geography	GC	country	North Macedonia	The former Yugoslav R	The former Yugoslav Republic of Macedonia
177	L	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Norway	Norway	Norway
178	L	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Oman	Oman	Oman
179	H	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Pakistan	Pakistan	Pakistan
180	L	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Palau	Palau	Palau
183	M	N=variation	geography	GC	area	Palestine	Palestine	Palestine
182	M	N=variation (FR)	geography	GC	area	Palestine	Palestine, State of	Palestine, State of
181	M	N=primary	geography	GC	area	Palestine	Palestine, State of	State of Palestine
184	M	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Panama	Panama	Panama
185	M	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Papua New Guin	Papua New Guinea	Papua New Guinea
186	M	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Paraguay	Paraguay	Paraguay
187	H	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Peru	Peru	Peru
188	H	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Philippines	Philippines	Philippines
189	L	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Poland	Poland	Poland
190	L	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Portugal	Portugal	Portugal
191	M	N=primary	geography	GC	area	Pridnestrovian M	Pridnestrovian Moldov	Pridnestrovian Moldovan Republic
192	M	N=variation	geography	GC	area	Pridnestrovian M	Transnistria	Transnistria
193	M	N=primary	geography	GC	area	Puntland	Puntland	Puntland
194	L	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Qatar	Qatar	Qatar
195	M	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Romania	Romania	Romania
196	L	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Romania	Romania	Romania
197	M	N=variation	geography	GC	country	Russia	Russia	Russia
198	M	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Russia	Russian Federation	Russian Federation
200	H	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Rwanda	Rwanda	Rwanda
201	M	N=primary	geography	GC	area	Sahrawi Arab De	Sahrawi Arab Democr	Sahrawi Arab Democratic Republic
202	M	N=variation	geography	GC	area	Sahrawi Arab De	Sahrawi Republic	Sahrawi Republic
203	M	N=variation	geography	GC	area	Sahrawi Arab De	Western Sahara	Western Sahara
204	L	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Saint Kitts and N	Saint Kitts and Nevis	Saint Kitts and Nevis

Keyword category "GC": countries and disputed territories								
id	priority	entry type	Category			Code		Lexemes
			category	short	sub-category	semantic value	unique code	English
205	M	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Saint Lucia	Saint Lucia	Saint Lucia
206	L	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Saint Vincent and the Grenadines	Saint Vincent and the Grenadines	Saint Vincent and the Grenadines
207	L	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Samoa	Samoa	Samoa
208	L	N=primary	geography	GC	country	San Marino	San Marino	San Marino
210	M	N=variation	geography	GC	area	São Tomé and Príncipe	Sao Tome and Principe	Sao Tome and Principe
209	M	N=primary	geography	GC	country	São Tomé and Príncipe	São Tomé and Príncipe	São Tomé and Príncipe
211	L	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Saudi Arabia	Saudi Arabia	Saudi Arabia
212	M	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Senegal	Senegal	Senegal
213	M	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Serbia	Serbia	Serbia
214	L	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Seychelles	Seychelles	Seychelles
215	H	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Sierra Leone	Sierra Leone	Sierra Leone
216	L	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Singapore	Singapore	Singapore
217	L	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Slovakia	Slovakia	Slovakia
218	L	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Slovenia	Slovenia	Slovenia
219	M	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Solomon Islands	Solomon Islands	Solomon Islands
220	M	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Somalia	Somalia	Somalia
221	M	N=primary	geography	GC	area	Somaliland	Somaliland	Somaliland
223	M	N=variation	geography	GC	country	South Africa	Republic of South Africa	Republic of South Africa
224	M	N=variation	geography	GC	country	South Africa	RSA	RSA
222	M	N=primary	geography	GC	country	South Africa	South Africa	South Africa
225	L	N=primary	geography	GC	country	South Korea	South Korea	South Korea
226	M	N=primary	geography	GC	area	South Ossetia	South Ossetia	South Ossetia
227	M	N=variation	geography	GC	area	South Ossetia	the State of Alania	the State of Alania
228	H	N=primary	geography	GC	country	South Sudan	South Sudan	South Sudan
229	L	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Spain	Spain	Spain
230	M	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Sri Lanka	Sri Lanka	Sri Lanka
231	H	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Sudan	Sudan	Sudan
232	M	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Suriname	Suriname	Suriname
233	M	N=variation (FR)	geography	GC	country	Suriname	Suriname	Suriname

Keyword category "GC": countries and disputed territories								
id	priority	entry type	Category			Code		Lexemes
			category	short	sub-category	semantic value	unique code	English
234	L	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Sweden	Sweden	Sweden
235	L	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Switzerland	Switzerland	Switzerland
237	M	N=variation	geography	GC	country	Syria	Syria	Syria
236	M	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Syria	Syrian Arab Republic	Syrian Arab Republic
238	M	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Tajikistan	Tajikistan	Tajikistan
240	M	N=variation	geography	GC	country	Tanzania	Tanzania	Tanzania
239	H	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Tanzania	United Republic of Tanzania	United Republic of Tanzania
241	M	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Thailand	Thailand	Thailand
242	M	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Tibet	Tibet	Tibet
243	M	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Togo	Togo	Togo
244	L	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Tonga	Tonga	Tonga
245	L	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Trinidad and Tobago	Trinidad and Tobago	Trinidad and Tobago
246	M	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Tunisia	Tunisia	Tunisia
247	M	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Turkey	Turkey	Turkey
248	M	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Turkmenistan	Turkmenistan	Turkmenistan
249	M	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Tuvalu	Tuvalu	Tuvalu
250	H	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Uganda	Uganda	Uganda
251	M	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Ukraine	Ukraine	Ukraine
252	L	N=primary	geography	GC	country	United Arab Emirates	United Arab Emirates	United Arab Emirates
253	L	N=primary	geography	GC	country	United Kingdom	United Kingdom	United Kingdom
254	L	N=primary	geography	GC	country	United States	United States	United States
255	L	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Uruguay	Uruguay	Uruguay
256	M	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Uzbekistan	Uzbekistan	Uzbekistan
257	M	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Vanuatu	Vanuatu	Vanuatu
258	L	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Vatican City	Vatican City	Vatican City
260	M	N=variation	geography	GC	country	Venezuela	Bolivarian Republic of Venezuela	Bolivarian Republic of Venezuela
259	M	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Venezuela	Venezuela	Venezuela
261	M	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Viet Nam	Viet Nam	Viet Nam
262	M	N=variation	geography	GC	country	Vietnam	Vietnam	Vietnam

Keyword category "GC": countries and disputed territories								
id	priority	entry type	Category			Code		Lexemes
			category	short	sub-category	semantic value	unique code	English
263	M	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Yemen	Yemen	Yemen
264	H	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Zambia	Zambia	Zambia
265	H	N=primary	geography	GC	country	Zimbabwe	Zimbabwe	Zimbabwe

Keyword category "GR": general geographic terms for world regions							
id	priority	Categories			Code		Lexemes
		category	short	sub-category	semantic value	unique code	English
1	M	geography	GR	region	Africa	Africa	Africa
2	M	geography	GR	region	Africa	AFR	AFR
3	M	geography	GR	region	Arab world	Arab world	Arab world
4	M	geography	GR	region	Asia-Pacific	Asia-Pacific	Asia-Pacific
5	M	geography	GR	region	Caribbean	Caribbean	Caribbean
6	M	geography	GR	region	Central Africa	Central Africa	Central Africa
7	M	geography	GR	region	Central America	Central America	Central America
8	M	geography	GR	region	Central Asia	Central Asia	Central Asia
9	M	geography	GR	region	East Africa	East Africa	East Africa
10	M	geography	GR	region	East Africa Community	East Africa Community	East Africa Community
11	M	geography	GR	region	East Africa Community	EAC	EAC
12	M	geography	GR	region	East Asia	East Asia	East Asia
13	M	geography	GR	region	East Asia and Pacific	East Asia and Pacific	East Asia and Pacific
14	M	geography	GR	region	East Asia and Pacific	EAP	EAP
15	M	geography	GR	region	Eastern Africa	Eastern Africa	Eastern Africa
16	M	geography	GR	region	Eastern Asia	Eastern Asia	Eastern Asia
17	M	geography	GR	region	Europe and Central Asia	Europe and Central Asia	Europe and Central Asia
18	M	geography	GR	region	Europe and Central Asia	ECA	ECA
19	M	geography	GR	region	Horn of Africa	Horn of Africa	Horn of Africa
20	M	geography	GR	region	Latin America	Latin America	Latin America
21	M	geography	GR	region	Latin America and Caribbean	Latin America and Caribbean	Latin America and Caribbean
22	M	geography	GR	region	Latin America and Caribbean	LAC	LAC
23	M	geography	GR	region	Micronesia	Micronesia	Micronesia
24	M	geography	GR	region	Middle Africa	Middle Africa	Middle Africa
25	M	geography	GR	region	Middle East	Middle East	Middle East
26	M	geography	GR	region	Middle East and North Africa	Middle East and North Africa	Middle East and North Africa
27	M	geography	GR	region	Middle East and North Africa	MENA	MENA

Keyword category "GR": general geographic terms for world regions							
id	priority	Categories			Code		Lexemes
		category	short	sub-category	semantic value	unique code	English
28	M	geography	GR	region	North Africa	North Africa	North Africa
29	M	geography	GR	region	Northern Africa	Northern Africa	Northern Africa
30	M	geography	GR	region	Pacific	Pacific	Pacific
31	M	geography	GR	region	Polynesia	Polynesia	Polynesia
32	M	geography	GR	region	Small Island Development	Small Island Development States	Small Island Development States
33	M	geography	GR	region	Small Island Development	SIDS	SIDS
34	M	geography	GR	region	Southern African Development	Southern African Development Community	Southern African Development Community
35	M	geography	GR	region	Southern African Development	SADC	SADC
36	M	geography	GR	region	South America	South America	South America
37	M	geography	GR	region	South Asia	South Asia	South Asia
38	M	geography	GR	region	South Asia Region	South Asia Region	South Asia Region
39	M	geography	GR	region	South Asia Region	SAR	SAR
40	M	geography	GR	region	Southeast Asia	Southeast Asia	Southeast Asia
41	M	geography	GR	region	Southeastern Asia	Southeastern Asia	Southeastern Asia
42	M	geography	GR	region	Southern Africa	southern Africa	Southern Africa
43	M	geography	GR	region	Southern Asia	Southern Asia	Southern Asia
44	M	geography	GR	region	Sub-Saharan Africa	SSA	SSA
45	M	geography	GR	region	Sub-Saharan Africa	Sub-Saharan Africa	Sub-Saharan Africa
46	M	geography	GR	region	West Africa	West Africa	West Africa
47	M	geography	GR	region	Western Africa	Western Africa	Western Africa
48	M	geography	GR	region	Western Asia	Western Asia	Western Asia

Keyword category "GD": development-related terms							
id	priority	Categories			Code		Lexemes
		category	short	sub-category	semantic value	unique code	English
1	M	development-related	GD	fragile and conflict context	conflict affected areas	conflict affected areas	conflict affected areas
2	M	development-related	GD	fragile and conflict context	conflict affected areas	conflict-affected areas	conflict-affected areas
3	M	development-related	GD	fragile and conflict context	conflict affected regions	conflict affected regions	conflict affected regions
4	M	development-related	GD	fragile and conflict context	conflict affected regions	conflict-affected regions	conflict-affected regions
5	M	development-related	GD	fragile and conflict context	conflict affected zones	conflict zones	conflict zones
6	M	development-related	GD	developing context	developing context	developing context	developing context
7	M	development-related	GD	developing context	developing countries	developing countries	developing countries
8	M	development-related	GD	developing context	developing country	developing country	developing country
9	M	development-related	GD	developing context	developing economies	developing economies	developing economies
10	M	development-related	GD	developing context	developing economy	developing economy	developing economy
11	M	development-related	GD	developing context	developing market countries	developing market countries	developing market countries
12	M	development-related	GD	developing context	developing market country	developing market country	developing market country
13	M	development-related	GD	developing context	developing markets	developing markets	developing markets
14	M	development-related	GD	developing context	developing nation	developing nation	developing nation
15	M	development-related	GD	developing context	developing region	developing region	developing region
16	M	development-related	GD	developing context	developing state	developing state	developing state
17	M	development-related	GD	developing context	developing world	developing world	developing world
18	M	development-related	GD	developing context	emergent nation	emergent nation	emergent nation
19	M	development-related	GD	developing context	emergent nations	emergent nations	emergent nations
20	M	development-related	GD	developing context	emerging economies	emerging economies	emerging economies
21	M	development-related	GD	developing context	emerging market countries	emerging market countries	emerging market countries
22	M	development-related	GD	developing context	emerging market country	emerging market country	emerging market country
23	M	development-related	GD	developing context	emerging nation	emerging nation	emerging nation
24	M	development-related	GD	developing context	emerging world	emerging world	emerging world
25	M	development-related	GD	fragile and conflict context	fragile and conflict affected areas	fragile and conflict affected areas	fragile and conflict affected areas
26	M	development-related	GD	fragile and conflict context	fragile and conflict affected region	fragile and conflict affected region	fragile and conflict affected region
27	M	development-related	GD	fragile and conflict context	fragile areas	fragile areas	fragile areas

Keyword category "GD": development-related terms							
id	priority	Categories			Code		Lexemes
		category	short	sub-category	semantic value	unique code	English
28	M	development-related	GD	fragile and conflict context	fragile contexts	fragile contexts	fragile contexts
29	M	development-related	GD	fragile and conflict context	fragile regions	fragile regions	fragile regions
30	M	development-related	GD	developing context	Global South	Global South	Global South
31	M	development-related	GD	developing context	growing econom	growing econom	growing economies
32	M	development-related	GD	developing context	less developed c	less developed c	less developed countries
33	M	development-related	GD	developing context	less developed c	less developed c	less developed country
34	M	development-related	GD	developing context	LMIC	LMIC	LMIC
35	M	development-related	GD	developing context	LMIC	LMICs	LMICs
36	M	development-related	GD	developing context	LMIC	low and middle in	low and middle income countries
37	M	development-related	GD	developing context	low income coun	low income coun	low income countries
38	M	development-related	GD	developing context	low income coun	low income coun	low income country
39	M	development-related	GD	developing context	low income envir	low income envir	low income environment
40	M	development-related	GD	developing context	low resource cou	low resource cou	low resource countries
41	M	development-related	GD	developing context	low resource cou	low resource cou	low resource country
42	M	development-related	GD	developing context	low resource env	low resource env	low resource environment
43	M	development-related	GD	developing context	low-income coun	low-income coun	low-income countries
44	M	development-related	GD	developing context	low-income coun	low-income coun	low-income country
45	M	development-related	GD	developing context	low-income envir	low-income envir	low-income environment
46	M	development-related	GD	developing context	low-resource cou	low-resource cou	low-resource countries
47	M	development-related	GD	developing context	low-resource cou	low-resource cou	low-resource country
48	M	development-related	GD	developing context	low-resource env	low-resource env	low-resource environment
49	M	development-related	GD	developing context	middle-income c	middle-income c	middle-income country
50	M	development-related	GD	developing context	middle-income c	middle-income c	middle-income country
51	M	development-related	GD	developing context	middle-income c	middle-income c	middle-income country
52	M	development-related	GD	developing context	middle-income e	middle-income e	middle-income environment
53	M	development-related	GD	developing context	middle-income e	middle income e	middle income environment
54	M	development-related	GD	developing context	third world	third world	third world

Keyword category "GD": development-related terms							
id	priority	Categories			Code		Lexemes
		category	short	sub-category	semantic value	unique code	English
55	M	development-related	GD	developing context	third world	third-world	third-world
56	M	development-related	GD	developing context	under developed	under developed	under developed countries
57	M	development-related	GD	developing context	under developed	under developed	under developed country
58	M	development-related	GD	developing context	under developed	under-developed	under-developed countries
59	M	development-related	GD	developing context	under developed	under-developed	under-developed country
60	M	development-related	GD	developing context	under developed	underdeveloped	underdeveloped countries
61	M	development-related	GD	developing context	under developed	underdeveloped	underdeveloped country
62	M	development-related	GD	developing context	under-developed	under-developed	under-developed nation
63	M	development-related	GD	developing context	under-developed	under developed	under developed nation
64	M	development-related	GD	developing context	under-developed	underdeveloped	underdeveloped nation

Keyword category "TT": tech-related terms only, which will need an education enabler (or relevant population specifier)							
id	priority	Categories			Code		Lexemes
		category	short	sub-category	semantic value	unique code	English
1	M	technology	TT	device	3D printer	3D printer	3D printer
2	M	technology	TT	device	3D printing	3D printing	3D printing
3	M	technology	TT	accessibility and inclusion	access to computers	access to computers	access to computers
4	M	technology	TT	accessibility and inclusion	accessible technologies	accessible technologies	accessible technologies
5	M	technology	TT	communication and social media	alternative communication	alternative communication	alternative communication
6	M	technology	TT	operating system	android	android	android
7	M	technology	TT	software	app	app	app
8	M	technology	TT	software	app	application	application
9	M	technology	TT	operating system	Apple	Apple	Apple
10	H	technology	TT	accessibility and inclusion	assistive technology	assistive technology	assistive technology
11	M	technology	TT	electronic resource	audio recording	audio recording	audio recording
12	M	technology	TT	communication and social media	augmentative communication	augmentative communication	augmentative communication
13	M	technology	TT	operating system	BADA	BADA	BADA
14	H	technology	TT	general ICT	bandwidth	bandwidth	bandwidth
15	M	technology	TT	accessibility and inclusion	barriers to technology	barriers to technology	barriers to technology
16	M	technology	TT	general ICT	big data	big data	big data
17	M	technology	TT	operating system	Blackberry	Blackberry	Blackberry
18	M	technology	TT	communication and social media	blog	blog	blog
19	M	technology	TT	device	camera	camera	camera
20	M	technology	TT	device	cellphone	cellphone	cellphone
21	M	technology	TT	communication and social media	Chatbot	Chatbot	Chatbot
22	M	technology	TT	device	clicker technology	clicker technology	clicker technology
23	M	technology	TT	device	clickers	clickers	clickers
24	M	technology	TT	electronic resource	cloud	cloud	cloud
25	M	technology	TT	communication and social media	CMC	CMC	CMC
26	M	technology	TT	general ICT	computational thinking literacy	computational thinking literacy	computational thinking literacy
27	H	technology	TT	device	computer	computer	computer
28	M	technology	TT	general ICT	computer illiteracy	computer illiteracy	computer illiteracy
29	M	technology	TT	general ICT	computer literacy	computer literacy	computer literacy
30	M	technology	TT	communication and social media	Computer-mediated communication	Computer-mediated communication	Computer-mediated communication
31	M	technology	TT	model of delivery	computerised	computerised	computerised
32	M	technology	TT	device	computers on wheels	computers on wheels	computers on wheels
33	M	technology	TT	device	computers on wheels	COWs	COWs
34	M	technology	TT	general ICT	Connectivity	Connectivity	Connectivity

35	M	technology	TT	general ICT	CT literacy	CT literacy	CT literacy
36	M	technology	TT	general ICT	data	data	data
37	M	technology	TT	communication and social media	digital communication	digital communication	digital communication
38	M	technology	TT	electronic resource	digital content	digital content	digital content
39	H	technology	TT	accessibility and inclusion	digital divide	digital divide	digital divide
40	M	technology	TT	accessibility and inclusion	digital exclusion	digital exclusion	digital exclusion
41	M	technology	TT	accessibility and inclusion	Digital immigrants	Digital immigrants	Digital immigrants
42	M	technology	TT	accessibility and inclusion	digital inclusion	digital inclusion	digital inclusion
43	H	technology	TT	general ICT	digital literacy	digital literacy	digital literacy
44	M	technology	TT	general ICT	Digital native	Digital native	Digital native
45	H	technology	TT	electronic resource	Digital resources	Digital resources	Digital resources
46	M	technology	TT	electronic resource	Digital scrapbook	Digital scrapbook	Digital scrapbook
47	?	technology	TT	general ICT	digital skills	digital skills	digital skills
48	M	technology	TT	model of delivery	digital storytelling	digital storytelling	digital storytelling
49	M	technology	TT	general ICT	digital technology	digital technology	digital technology
50	M	technology	TT	model of delivery	digital transformation	digital transformation	digital transformation
51	M	technology	TT	model of delivery	digitalised	digitalised	digitalised
52	M	technology	TT	model of delivery	digitised	digitised	digitised
53	M	technology	TT	communication and social media	Discord	Discord	Discord
54	M	technology	TT	general ICT	Disruptive technology	Disruptive technology	Disruptive technology
55	M	technology	TT	communication and social media	Douban	Douban	Douban
56	M	technology	TT	communication and social media	Douyin	Douyin	Douyin
57	M	technology	TT	device	DVD player	DVD player	DVD player
58	H	technology	TT	electronic resource	e-book	e-book	e-book
59	H	technology	TT	device	e-reader	e-reader	e-reader
60	M	technology	TT	device	earphones	earphones	earphones
61	H	technology	TT	electronic resource	Ebook	Ebook	Ebook
62	H	technology	TT	device	ereader	ereader	ereader
63	M	technology	TT	communication and social media	Facebook	Facebook	Facebook
65	H	technology	TT	device	gadget	gadget	gadget
66	M	technology	TT	device	game console	game console	game console
67	M	technology	TT	operating system	Garnet	Garnet	Garnet
68	M	technology	TT	software	Geographical information systems	Geographical information systems	Geographical information systems
69	M	technology	TT	device	hardware	hardware	hardware
70	M	technology	TT	device	headphones	headphones	headphones
71	M	technology	TT	electronic resource	holograms	holograms	holograms
72	M	technology	TT	device	i-pad	i-pad	i-pad
73	M	technology	TT	general ICT	ICT	ICT	ICT

74	M	technology	TT	general ICT	ICT	ICT goods and services	ICT goods and services
75	H	technology	TT	general ICT	ICT	information and communication technologies	information and communication technology
76	M	technology	TT	accessibility and inclusion	inclusive technologies	inclusive technologies	inclusive technologies
77	M	technology	TT	general ICT	influence of technology	influence of technology	influence of technology
78	M	technology	TT	general ICT	Information communications technology literacy	Information communications technology literacy	Information communications technology literacy
79	M	technology	TT	general ICT	information literacy	information literacy	information literacy
81	M	technology	TT	communication and social media	Instagram	Instagram	Instagram
82	M	technology	TT	software	instructional systems	instructional systems	instructional systems
83	M	technology	TT	software	instructional technology	instructional technology	instructional technology
84	M	technology	TT	general ICT	integration of technology	integration of technology	integration of technology
85	M	technology	TT	operating system	intel	intel	intel
86	M	technology	TT	model of delivery	interactive	interactive	interactive
87	M	technology	TT	electronic resource	Internet	Internet	Internet
88	M	technology	TT	accessibility and inclusion	internet access	internet access	internet access
89	M	technology	TT	electronic resource	internet domain	internet domain	internet domain
90	H	technology	TT	general ICT	internet of things	internet of things	internet of things
91	M	technology	TT	operating system	IOS	IOS	IOS
92	M	technology	TT	device	ipad	ipad	ipad
93	M	technology	TT	device	iphone	iphone	iphone
95	M	technology	TT	general ICT	information technology	I.T.	I.T.
96	M	technology	TT	general ICT	information technology	IT	IT
97	M	technology	TT	general ICT	information technology	information technology	information technology
98	M	technology	TT	device	keyboard	keyboard	keyboard
99	M	technology	TT	device	kindle	kindle	kindle
100	M	technology	TT	device	laptop	laptop	laptop
101	M	technology	TT	communication and social media	LinkedIn	LinkedIn	LinkedIn
102	M	technology	TT	operating system	Maemo	Maemo	Maemo
103	M	technology	TT	operating system	MeeGo	MeeGo	MeeGo
104	M	technology	TT	general ICT	metadata	metadata	metadata
105	M	technology	TT	operating system	microsoft	microsoft	microsoft
106	H	technology	TT	device	mobile phone	mobile phone	mobile phone
107	M	technology	TT	communication and social media	new media	new media	new media
108	M	technology	TT	general ICT	new technologies	new technologies	new technologies
109	M	technology	TT	general ICT	offline	offline	offline
110	M	technology	TT	general ICT	online	online	online
111	M	technology	TT	communication and social media	online discussion	online discussion	online discussion
112	M	technology	TT	model of delivery	online lab	online lab	online lab
113	M	technology	TT	software	open source	open source	open source

114	M	technology	TT	software	open source software	open source software	open source software
115	M	technology	TT	operating system	Open wedOS	Open wedOS	Open wedOS
116	M	technology	TT	operating system	operating system	operating system	operating system
117	M	technology	TT	operating system	Palm OS	Palm OS	Palm OS
118	M	technology	TT	communication and social media	Pinterest	Pinterest	Pinterest
119	M	technology	TT	software	platform	platform	platform
120	M	technology	TT	communication and social media	podcast	podcast	podcast
121	M	technology	TT	software	Poll Everywhere	Poll Everywhere	Poll Everywhere
122	M	technology	TT	device	printer	printer	printer
123	M	technology	TT	communication and social media	QQ	QQ	QQ
124	M	technology	TT	communication and social media	QZone	QZone	QZone
125	M	technology	TT	device	RACHEL	RACHEL	RACHEL
126	M	technology	TT	device	RACHEL server	RACHEL server	RACHEL server
127	M	technology	TT	device	radio	radio	radio
128	H	technology	TT	device	Raspberry Pi	Raspberry Pi	Raspberry Pi
129	M	technology	TT	communication and social media	Reddit	Reddit	Reddit
130	M	technology	TT	device	SD card	SD card	SD card
131	M	technology	TT	electronic resource	simulation	simulation	simulation
132	M	technology	TT	communication and social media	Sina Weibo	Sina Weibo	Sina Weibo
133	M	technology	TT	device	single board computer	single board computer	single board computer
134	M	technology	TT	communication and social media	Snapchat	Snapchat	Snapchat
135	H	technology	TT	communication and social media	social media	social media	social media
136	M	technology	TT	communication and social media	social network	social network	social network
137	M	technology	TT	communication and social media	social networking sites	social networking sites	social networking sites
138	M	technology	TT	software	software	software	software
139	M	technology	TT	accessibility and inclusion	supportive technology	supportive technology	supportive technology
140	M	technology	TT	operating system	Symbian	Symbian	Symbian
141	H	technology	TT	device	tablet	tablet	tablet
142	M	technology	TT	general ICT	technological literacy	technological literacy	technological literacy
143	M	technology	TT	general ICT	technology leapfrogging	technology leapfrogging	technology leapfrogging
144	M	technology	TT	model of delivery	technology-enhanced	technology-enhanced	technology-enhanced
145	M	technology	TT	device	telephone	telephone	telephone
146	M	technology	TT	device	television	television	television
147	M	technology	TT	communication and social media	TikTok	TikTok	TikTok
148	M	technology	TT	device	television	TV	TV
149	M	technology	TT	communication and social media	Twitter	Twitter	Twitter
150	M	technology	TT	operating system	Verdict	Verdict	Verdict
151	M	technology	TT	communication and social media	Viber	Viber	Viber

152	M	technology	TT	device	video recorder	video recorder	video recorder
153	M	technology	TT	software	videoconferencing	videoconferencing	videoconferencing
154	M	technology	TT	electronic resource	virtual peer	virtual peer	virtual peer
155	M	technology	TT	electronic resource	Virtual reality	VR	VR
156	M	technology	TT	electronic resource	Virtual reality	Virtual reality	Virtual reality
157	M	technology	TT	electronic resource	Web	Web	Web
158	M	technology	TT	communication and social media	WeChat	WeChat	WeChat
159	H	technology	TT	communication and social media	WhatsApp	WhatsApp	WhatsApp
160	M	technology	TT	general ICT	WiFi	WiFi	WiFi
161	M	technology	TT	electronic resource	Wikipedia	Wikipedia	Wikipedia
162	M	technology	TT	operating system	Windows	Windows	Windows
163	M	technology	TT	communication and social media	Youtube	Youtube	Youtube

Keyword category "TE": terms that include both technology and education							
id	priority	Categories			Code		Lexemes
		category	short	sub-category	semantic value	unique code	English
1	M	edtech	TE	device	electronic whiteboard	electronic whiteboard	electronic whiteboard
2	M	edtech	TE	device	interactive whiteboard	interactive whiteboard	interactive whiteboard
3	H	edtech	TE	device	smart board	smart board	smart board
4	M	edtech	TE	device	smartboard	smartboard	smartboard
5	M	edtech	TE	electronic resour	electronic textbook	e textbook	e textbook
6	H	edtech	TE	electronic resour	electronic textbook	e-textbook	e-textbook
7	M	edtech	TE	electronic resour	electronic textbook	electronic textbook	electronic textbook
8	M	edtech	TE	electronic resour	electronic textbook	etextbook	etextbook
9	M	edtech	TE	electronic resour	Etutor	e-tutor	e-tutor
10	M	edtech	TE	electronic resour	Etutor	Etutor	Etutor
11	M	edtech	TE	electronic resour	free digital resources	FDR	FDR
12	M	edtech	TE	electronic resour	free digital resources	free digital resources	free digital resources
13	M	edtech	TE	electronic resour	Intelligent agent	Intelligent agent	Intelligent agent
14	M	edtech	TE	electronic resour	Intelligent tutoring system	Intelligent tutoring system	Intelligent tutoring system
15	M	edtech	TE	electronic resour	Learning platform	Learning platform	Learning platform
16	M	edtech	TE	electronic resour	massive open online course	MOOC	MOOC
17	M	edtech	TE	electronic resour	massive open online course	MOOCs	MOOCs
18	M	technology	TT	electronic resour	moodle	moodle	moodle
19	M	edtech	TE	electronic resour	open educational resources	OER	OER
20	M	edtech	TE	electronic resour	open educational resources	open educational resources	open educational resources
21	M	edtech	TE	electronic resour	online textbook	online textbook	online textbook
22	H	edtech	TE	electronic resour	Online tutor	Online tutor	Online tutor
23	H	edtech	TE	electronic resour	Reusable learning object	Reusable learning object	Reusable learning object
24	H	edtech	TE	electronic resour	Reusable learning object	RLO	RLO
25	H	edtech	TE	electronic resour	School website	School website	School website
26	M	edtech	TE	general edtech	EdTech	EdTech	EdTech
27	H	edtech	TE	general edtech	EdTech	Education Technology	Education Technology
28	M	edtech	TE	general edtech	EdTech	Educational Technology	Educational Technology
29	M	edtech	TE	general edtech	educational innovation	educational innovation	educational innovation
30	H	edtech	TE	general edtech	Educational technologies	Educational technologies	Educational technologies

Keyword category "TE": terms that include both technology and education							
id	priority	Categories			Code		Lexemes
		category	short	sub-category	semantic value	unique code	English
31	H	edtech	TE	general edtech	Emerging education technologies	Emerging education technologies	Emerging education technologies
32	H	edtech	TE	general edtech	Emerging education technology	Emerging education technology	Emerging education technology
33	H	edtech	TE	general edtech	ICT in classrooms	ICT in classrooms	ICT in classrooms
34	H	edtech	TE	general edtech	ICT in the classroom	ICT in the classroom	ICT in the classroom
35	H	edtech	TE	general edtech	technology at school	technology at school	technology at school
36	H	edtech	TE	general edtech	technology in education	technology in education	technology in education
37	H	edtech	TE	general edtech	technology in school	technology in school	technology in school
38	H	edtech	TE	general edtech	technology use in education	technology use in education	technology use in education
39	M	edtech	TE	model of delivery	adaptive learning	adaptive learning	adaptive learning
40	H	edtech	TE	model of delivery	asynchronous learning	asynchronous learning	asynchronous learning
41	M	edtech	TE	model of delivery	blended learning	blended learning	blended learning
42	H	edtech	TE	model of delivery	Computer assisted instruction	CAI	CAI
43	H	edtech	TE	model of delivery	computer assisted instruction	computer assisted instruction	computer assisted instruction
44	H	edtech	TE	model of delivery	computer assisted instruction	computer-assisted instruction	computer-assisted instruction
45	H	edtech	TE	model of delivery	Computer assisted learning	CAL	CAL
46	H	edtech	TE	model of delivery	Computer assisted learning	Computer assisted learning	Computer assisted learning
47	H	edtech	TE	model of delivery	computer based assessment	computer based assessment	computer based assessment
48	H	edtech	TE	model of delivery	computer based instruction	computer based instruction	computer based instruction
49	M	edtech	TE	model of delivery	computer based instruction	computer-based instruction	computer-based instruction
50	M	edtech	TE	model of delivery	computer managed instruction	computer managed instruction	computer managed instruction
51	M	edtech	TE	model of delivery	computer mediated learning	computer mediated learning	computer mediated learning
52	H	edtech	TE	model of delivery	computer mediated learning	computer-mediated learning	computer-mediated learning
53	M	edtech	TE	model of delivery	Computer supported collaborative learning	Computer supported collaborative learning	Computer supported collaborative learning
54	M	edtech	TE	model of delivery	computer supported education	computer supported education	computer supported education
55	M	edtech	TE	model of delivery	computer supported education	computer-supported education	computer-supported education
56	H	edtech	TE	model of delivery	Computer-assisted instructional programme	Computer-assisted instructional programme	Computer-assisted instructional programme
57	H	edtech	TE	model of delivery	computerised learning	computerised learning	computerised learning
58	M	edtech	TE	model of delivery	computerised learning	computerized learning	computerized learning
59	H	edtech	TE	model of delivery	connected learning	connected learning	connected learning
60	H	edtech	TE	model of delivery	Differentiated learning	Differentiated learning	Differentiated learning

Keyword category "TE": terms that include both technology and education							
id	priority	Categories			Code		Lexemes
		category	short	sub-category	semantic value	unique code	English
61	H	edtech	TE	model of delivery	digital learning	digital learning	digital learning
62	H	edtech	TE	model of delivery	digital learning	digital-learning	digital-learning
63	H	edtech	TE	model of delivery	distance education	distance education	distance education
64	M	edtech	TE	model of delivery	distance learning	distance learning	distance learning
65	M	edtech	TE	model of delivery	distance learning program	distance learning program	distance learning program
66	M	edtech	TE	model of delivery	distributed learning	distributed learning	distributed learning
67	M	edtech	TE	model of delivery	e-learning	e-learning	e-learning
68	M	edtech	TE	model of delivery	e-learning	elearning	elearning
69	H	edtech	TE	model of delivery	e-learning	electronic learning	electronic learning
71	H	edtech	TE	model of delivery	electronic classroom	electronic classroom	electronic classroom
72	H	edtech	TE	model of delivery	flipped classroom	flipped classroom	flipped classroom
73	H	edtech	TE	model of delivery	flipped learning	flipped learning	flipped learning
75	H	edtech	TE	model of delivery	free digital learning	FDL	FDL
76	H	edtech	TE	model of delivery	free digital learning	free digital learning	free digital learning
77	H	edtech	TE	model of delivery	gamification	gamification	gamification
78	H	edtech	TE	model of delivery	hybrid learning	H-learning	H-learning
79	H	edtech	TE	model of delivery	hybrid learning	hybrid learning	hybrid learning
80	M	edtech	TE	model of delivery	Individualised learning	Individualised learning	Individualised learning
81	M	edtech	TE	model of delivery	instructional innovation	instructional innovation	instructional innovation
82	M	edtech	TE	model of delivery	instructional technology	instructional technology	instructional technology
83	M	edtech	TE	model of delivery	integrated learning systems	integrated learning systems	integrated learning systems
84	H	edtech	TE	model of delivery	Interactive learning environment	Interactive learning environment	Interactive learning environment
85	H	edtech	TE	model of delivery	learning	ubiquitous learning	ubiquitous learning
86	H	edtech	TE	model of delivery	media literacy	media literacy	media literacy
87	H	edtech	TE	model of delivery	microlearning	micro learning	micro learning
88	H	edtech	TE	model of delivery	microlearning	micro-learning	micro-learning
89	H	edtech	TE	model of delivery	microlearning	microlearning	microlearning
90	H	edtech	TE	model of delivery	mobile education	m education	m education
91	H	edtech	TE	model of delivery	mobile education	m-education	m-education
92	M	edtech	TE	model of delivery	mobile education	meducation	meducation

Keyword category "TE": terms that include both technology and education							
id	priority	Categories			Code		Lexemes
		category	short	sub-category	semantic value	unique code	English
93	M	edtech	TE	model of delivery	mobile education	mobile education	mobile education
94	M	edtech	TE	model of delivery	mobile learning	m learning	m learning
95	M	edtech	TE	model of delivery	mobile learning	m-learning	m-learning
96	H	edtech	TE	model of delivery	mobile learning	mlearning	mlearning
98	H	edtech	TE	model of delivery	mobile learning	Mobile learning	Mobile learning
99	M	edtech	TE	model of delivery	multimedia instruction	multimedia instruction	multimedia instruction
100	M	edtech	TE	model of delivery	open and distance elearning	ODEL	ODEL
101	M	edtech	TE	model of delivery	open and distance learning	ODL	ODL
102	M	edtech	TE	model of delivery	online course	online course	online course
103	M	edtech	TE	model of delivery	online lab	online lab	online lab
104	M	edtech	TE	model of delivery	online laboratory	online laboratory	online laboratory
105	H	edtech	TE	model of delivery	online learning	online learning	online learning
106	H	edtech	TE	model of delivery	open and distance elearning	open and distance elearning	open and distance elearning
107	H	edtech	TE	model of delivery	open and distance elearning	open and distance e-learning	open and distance e-learning
108	H	edtech	TE	model of delivery	open and distance learning	open and distance learning	open and distance learning
109	M	edtech	TE	model of delivery	open education	open education	open education
110	H	edtech	TE	model of delivery	open learning	open learning	open learning
111	M	edtech	TE	model of delivery	personalised learning	personalised learning	personalised learning
112	M	edtech	TE	model of delivery	personalised teaching	personalised teaching	personalised teaching
113	M	edtech	TE	model of delivery	Plasma-based instruction	Plasma-based instruction	Plasma-based instruction
114	M	edtech	TE	model of delivery	Self-directed learning	Self-directed learning	Self-directed learning
115	M	edtech	TE	model of delivery	self-paced learning	self-paced learning	self-paced learning
116	H	edtech	TE	model of delivery	Synchronous online learning	Synchronous online learning	Synchronous online learning
117	H	edtech	TE	model of delivery	technological pedagogical content	technological pedagogical content	technological pedagogical content
118	H	edtech	TE	model of delivery	technology assisted learning	technology assisted learning	technology assisted learning
119	H	edtech	TE	model of delivery	Technology engagement teaching strategy	Technology engagement teaching strategy	Technology engagement teaching strategy
120	M	edtech	TE	model of delivery	Technology engagement teaching strategy	TETS	TETS
121	M	edtech	TE	model of delivery	Technology enhanced learning	Technology enhanced learning	Technology enhanced learning
122	M	edtech	TE	model of delivery	Technology enhanced learning	Technology-enhanced learning	Technology-enhanced learning
123	H	edtech	TE	model of delivery	Technology enhanced learning	TEL	TEL

Keyword category "TE": terms that include both technology and education							
id	priority	Categories			Code		Lexemes
		category	short	sub-category	semantic value	unique code	English
124	H	edtech	TE	model of delivery	technology integration	technology integration	technology integration
125	M	edtech	TE	model of delivery	technology-assisted learning	technology-assisted learning	technology-assisted learning
126	M	edtech	TE	model of delivery	tele education	tele education	tele education
127	H	edtech	TE	model of delivery	tele education	tele-education	tele-education
128	H	edtech	TE	model of delivery	tele education	teleeducation	teleeducation
129	H	edtech	TE	model of delivery	virtual classroom	virtual classroom	virtual classroom
130	H	edtech	TE	model of delivery	virtual learning	virtual learning	virtual learning
131	H	edtech	TE	model of delivery	virtual learning environment	virtual learning environment	virtual learning environment
132	M	edtech	TE	model of delivery	virtual learning environment	VLE	VLE
133	H	edtech	TE	model of delivery	Virtual school	Virtual school	Virtual school
134	H	edtech	TE	model of delivery	web based instruction	web based instruction	web based instruction
135	M	edtech	TE	model of delivery	web based instruction	web-based instruction	web-based instruction
136	M	edtech	TE	model of delivery	webinar	webinar	webinar
137	M	edtech	TE	software	Course Management System	CMS	CMS
139	M	edtech	TE	software	Course Management System	Course Management System	Course Management System
140	H	edtech	TE	software	Education Management Information System	Education Management Information System	Education Management Information S
141	M	edtech	TE	software	Education Management Information System	EMIS	EMIS
142	H	edtech	TE	software	examination systems	examination systems	examination systems
143	H	edtech	TE	software	learning management systems	learning management system	learning management system
144	M	edtech	TE	software	learning management systems	LMS	LMS
145	M	edtech	TE	software	massive open online course	massive open online course	massive open online course
146	M	edtech	TE	software	Teacher development software	Teacher development software	Teacher development software
147	M	edtech	TE	software	textbook analytics	textbook analytics	textbook analytics

Keyword category "P1": this sheet refers to the level of education of the target population (i.e. ECE, basic education, and teacher and school staff education)							
id	priority	Categories			Code		Lexemes
		category	short	sub-category	semantic value	unique code	English
1	M	population	P1	primary and secondary education	classroom assistants	classroom assistants	classroom assistants
2	M	population	P1	primary and secondary education	classroom instruction	classroom instruction	classroom instruction
3	M	population	P1	primary and secondary education	classroom teaching	classroom teaching	classroom teaching
4	H	population	P1	government	district education officer	district education officer	district education officer
5	M	population	P1	early childhood education	early childhood development	early childhood development	early childhood development
6	H	population	P1	early childhood education	early childhood education	early childhood education	early childhood education
7	H	population	P1	early childhood education	early childhood education	ECE	ECE
8	M	population	P1	teacher and school staff education	educators	educators	educators
9	M	population	P1	primary and secondary education	elementary education	elementary education	elementary education
10	H	population	P1	primary and secondary education	elementary school	elementary school	elementary school
11	M	population	P1	primary and secondary education	faith school	faith school	faith school
12	H	population	P1	teacher and school staff education	headteacher	headteacher	headteacher
13	H	population	P1	primary and secondary education	high school	high school	high school
14	H	population	P1	primary and secondary education	junior middle school	junior middle school	junior middle school
15	H	population	P1	primary and secondary education	junior school	junior school	junior school
16	H	population	P1	primary and secondary education	k-12	k to 12	k to 12
17	H	population	P1	primary and secondary education	k-12	k-12	k-12
18	H	population	P1	early childhood education	kindergarten	kindergarten	kindergarten
19	H	population	P1	primary and secondary education	lower secondary	lower secondary	lower secondary
20	H	population	P1	primary and secondary education	middle school	middle school	middle school
21	H	population	P1	primary and secondary education	middle-school	middle-school	middle-school
22	H	population	P1	government	ministry of education	ministry of education	ministry of education
23	H	population	P1	government	ministry of education	MoE	MoE
24	H	population	P1	early childhood education	nursery	nursery	nursery
25	H	population	P1	primary and secondary education	post primary	post primary	post primary
26	H	population	P1	primary and secondary education	post-primary	post-primary	post-primary
27	H	population	P1	early childhood education	pre primary	pre primary	pre primary
28	H	population	P1	early childhood education	pre-primary	pre-primary	pre-primary
29	H	population	P1	early childhood education	pre-school	pre-school	pre-school
30	H	population	P1	teacher and school staff education	pre-service teachers	pre-service teachers	pre-service teachers
31	H	population	P1	primary and secondary education	primary education	primary education	primary education
32	H	population	P1	primary and secondary education	primary school	primary school	primary school
33	H	population	P1	teacher and school staff education	principal	principal	principal
34	M	population	P1	primary and secondary education	private school	private school	private school

Keyword category "P1": this sheet refers to the level of education of the target population (i.e. ECE, basic education, and teacher and school staff education)							
id	priority	Categories			Code		Lexemes
		category	short	sub-category	semantic value	unique code	English
35	M	population	P1	teacher and school staff edu	refugee educator	refugee educator	refugee educator
36	H	population	P1	primary and secondary educ	school	school	school
37	M	population	P1	teacher and school staff edu	school administrator	school administrator	school administrator
38	M	population	P1	teacher and school staff edu	school authority	school authority	school authority
39	M	population	P1	teacher and school staff edu	school director	school director	school director
40	H	population	P1	government	school governing body	school governing body	school governing body
41	H	population	P1	teacher and school staff edu	school head	school head	school head
42	H	population	P1	teacher and school staff edu	school leadership team	school leadership team	school leadership team
43	H	population	P1	teacher and school staff edu	school management team	school management team	school management team
44	H	population	P1	teacher and school staff edu	school official	school official	school official
45	H	population	P1	teacher and school staff edu	school principal	school principal	school principal
46	M	population	P1	teacher and school staff edu	school supervisor	school supervisor	school supervisor
47	H	population	P1	teacher and school staff edu	school teacher	school teacher	school teacher
48	H	population	P1	primary and secondary educ	secondary education	secondary education	secondary education
49	H	population	P1	primary and secondary educ	secondary school	secondary school	secondary school
50	H	population	P1	teacher and school staff edu	senior leadership team	senior leadership team	senior leadership team
51	M	population	P1	primary and secondary educ	state school	state school	state school
52	H	population	P1	teacher and school staff edu	teacher candidates	teacher candidates	teacher candidates
53	H	population	P1	teacher and school staff edu	teacher certificate	teacher certificate	teacher certificate
54	H	population	P1	teacher and school staff edu	teacher COP	teacher community of practice	teacher community of practice
55	H	population	P1	teacher and school staff edu	teacher COP	teacher communities of practice	teacher communities of practice
56	H	population	P1	teacher and school staff edu	teacher COP	teacher COP	teacher COP
57	H	population	P1	teacher and school staff edu	teacher education	teacher education	teacher education
58	H	population	P1	teacher and school staff edu	teacher professional development	teacher professional development	teacher professional development
59	H	population	P1	teacher and school staff edu	teacher professional development	TPD	TPD
60	H	population	P1	teacher and school staff edu	teacher training	teacher training	teacher training
61	H	population	P1	teacher and school staff edu	teacher training centre	teacher training centre	teacher training centre
62	H	population	P1	teacher and school staff edu	teacher training college	teacher training college	teacher training college
63	H	population	P1	teacher and school staff edu	teacher training institute	teacher training institute	teacher training institute
64	H	population	P1	teacher and school staff edu	teachers	teachers	teachers
65	M	population	P1	teacher and school staff edu	teaching assistant	teaching assistant	teaching assistant
66	M	population	P1	teacher and school staff edu	teaching assistant	teaching assistant	teaching assistant
67	M	population	P1	teacher and school staff edu	teaching assistants	teaching assistants	teaching assistants
68	H	population	P1	teacher and school staff edu	teaching certificate	teaching certificate	teaching certificate

Keyword category "P2": includes education types and levels that will need to be run against additional population specifiers (sheet P1). See target specifiers in row 'I'.								
id	priority		Categories			Code		Lexemes
			category	short	sub-category	semantic value	unique code	English
1	M	Q=P1/population	population	P2	accessibility and inclu	accessible learning	accessible learning	accessible learning
2	M	Q=P1/population	population	P2	accessibility and inclu	alien	alien	alien
3	M	Q=P1/population	population	P2	accessibility and inclu	alienation	alienation	alienation
4	M	Q=P1/population	population	P2	education in emergen	asylum	asylum	asylum
5	M	Q=P1/population	population	P2	education in emergen	asylum seeker	asylum seeker	asylum seeker
6	M	Q=P1/population	population	P2	accessibility and inclu	at-risk population	at-risk population	at-risk population
7	M	Q=P1/population	population	P2	teacher and school st	bachelor's degree	bachelor's degree	bachelor's degree
8	M	Q=P1/population	population	P2	teacher and school st	bachelors degree	bachelors degree	bachelors degree
9	M	Q=P1/population	population	P2	teacher and school st	career-entry support	career-entry support	career-entry support
10	M	Q=P1/population	population	P2	teacher and school st	career entry support	career entry support	career entry support
11	M	Q=P1/population	population	P2	teacher and school st	career path training	career path training	career path training
12	M	Q=P1/population	population	P2	informal education	church	church	church
13	M	Q=P1/population	population	P2	informal education	community education	community education	community education
14	M	Q=P1/population	population	P2	teacher and school st	competency-based training	competency-based traini	competency-based training
15	M	Q=P1/population	population	P2	teacher and school st	continuing education	continuing education	continuing education
16	M	Q=P1/population	population	P2	teacher and school st	continuing training	continuing training	continuing training
17	M	Q=P1/population	population	P2	teacher and school st	continuous professional developme	continuous professional	continuous professional developm
18	M	Q=P1/population	population	P2	teacher and school st	continuous professional developme	CPD	CPD
19	M	Q=P1/population	population	P2	teacher and school st	degree	degree	degree
20	M	Q=P1/population	population	P2	teacher and school st	diploma	diploma	diploma
21	M	Q=P1/population	population	P2	accessibility and inclu	disabilities	disabilities	disabilities
22	M	Q=P1/population	population	P2	accessibility and inclu	disability	disability	disability
23	M	Q=P1/population	population	P2	primary and secondar	district-level	district-level	district-level
24	M	Q=P1/population	population	P2	education in emergen	displaced person	displaced person	displaced person
25	M	Q=P1/population	population	P2	education in emergen	displaced populations	displaced populations	displaced populations
26	M	Q=P1/population	population	P2	primary and secondar	education	education	education
27	M	Q=P1/population	population	P2	education in emergen	education in emergencies	education in emergencie	education in emergencies
28	M	Q=P1/population	population	P2	education in emergen	education in emergencies	EiE	EiE
29	M	Q=P1/population	population	P2	informal education	favela	favela	favela

30	M	Q=P1/population	population	P2	education in emergen	fragility in education	fragility in education	fragility in education
31	M	Q=P1/population	population	P2	informal education	gang members	gang members	gang members
32	M	Q=P1/population	population	P2	primary and secondar	geographically dispersed	geographically dispersed	geographically dispersed
33	M	Q=P1/population	population	P2	teacher and school st	in-service training	in-service training	in-service training
34	M	Q=P1/population	population	P2	informal education	informal education	informal education	informal education
35	M	Q=P1/population	population	P2	informal education	informal learning	informal learning	informal learning
36	M	Q=P1/population	population	P2	informal education	informal training	informal training	informal training
37	M	Q=P1/population	population	P2	subject	language learning	language learning	language learning
38	M	Q=P1/population	population	P2	teacher and school st	learning community	learning community	learning community
39	M	Q=P1/population	population	P2	teacher and school st	master's degree	master's degree	master's degree
40	M	Q=P1/population	population	P2	teacher and school st	masters	masters degree	masters
41	M	Q=P1/population	population	P2	subject	math	math	math
42	M	Q=P1/population	population	P2	subject	mathematics	mathematics	mathematics
43	M	Q=P1/population	population	P2	accessibility and inclu	migrant	migrant	migrant
44	M	Q=P1/population	population	P2	accessibility and inclu	minority ethnic group	minority ethnic group	minority ethnic group
45	M	Q=P1/population	population	P2	informal education	mosque	mosque	mosque
46	M	Q=P1/population	population	P2	accessibility and inclu	moving populations	moving populations	moving populations
47	M	Q=P1/population	population	P2	subject	natural science	natural science	natural science
48	M	Q=P1/population	population	P2	informal education	Non-formal education	Non-formal education	Non-formal education
49	M	Q=P1/population	population	P2	informal education	Non-formal education	NFE	NFE
50	M	Q=P1/population	population	P2	informal education	non-formal learning	non-formal learning	non-formal learning
51	M	Q=P1/population	population	P2	teacher and school st	Postsecondary Education	Postsecondary Educatio	Postsecondary Education
52	M	Q=P1/population	population	P2	teacher and school st	pre-service training	pre-service training	pre-service training
53	M	Q=P1/population	population	P2	teacher and school st	professional continuing education	professional continuing e	professional continuing education
54	M	Q=P1/population	population	P2	teacher and school st	professional education	professional education	professional education
55	M	Q=P1/population	population	P2	teacher and school st	professional learning community	professional learning cor	professional learning community
56	M	Q=P1/population	population	P2	teacher and school st	professional learning community	professional learning cor	professional learning communities
57	M	Q=P1/population	population	P2	teacher and school st	professional qualification	professional qualification	professional qualification
58	M	Q=P1/population	population	P2	teacher and school st	professional re-education	professional re-educatio	professional re-education
59	M	Q=P1/population	population	P2	teacher and school st	professional studies	professional studies	professional studies
60	M	Q=P1/population	population	P2	teacher and school st	professional training	professional training	professional training
61	M	Q=P1/population	population	P2	teacher and school st	qualification	qualification	qualification

62	M	Q=P1/population	population	P2	education in emergen	refugee education	refugee education	refugee education
63	M	Q=P1/population	population	P2	education in emergen	refugee learning	refugee learning	refugee learning
64	M	Q=P1/population	population	P2	subject	science	science	science
65	M	Q=P1/population	population	P2	subject	science and technology	science and technology	science and technology
66	M	Q=P1/population	population	P2	subject	Science Technology Engineering ar	Science Technology Eng	Science Technology Engineering
67	M	Q=P1/population	population	P2	subject	Science Technology Engineering ar	Science Technology Eng	Science Technology Engineering
68	M	Q=P1/population	population	P2	informal education	slum	slum	slum
69	M	Q=P1/population	population	P2	accessibility and inclu	special educational needs	special educational need	special educational needs
70	M	Q=P1/population	population	P2	accessibility and inclu	special educational needs	SEN	SEN
71	M	Q=P1/population	population	P2	accessibility and inclu	SEN learner	SEN learner	SEN learner
72	M	Q=P1/population	population	P2	accessibility and inclu	SEN student	SEN student	SEN student
73	M	Q=P1/population	population	P2	accessibility and inclu	special educational needs and disa	special educational need	special educational needs and dis
74	M	Q=P1/population	population	P2	accessibility and inclu	special educational needs and disa	SEND	SEND
75	M	Q=P1/population	population	P2	accessibility and inclu	special needs students	special needs students	special needs students
76	M	Q=P1/population	population	P2	subject	Science Technology Engineering ar	STEAM	STEAM
77	M	Q=P1/population	population	P2	subject	Science Technology Engineering ar	STEM	STEM
78	M	Q=P1/population	population	P2	informal education	street children	street children	street children
79	M	Q=P1/population	population	P2	primary and secondar	students	students	students
80	M	Q=P1/population	population	P2	accessibility and inclu	students with disabilities	students with disabilities	students with disabilities
81	M	Q=P1/population	population	P2	primary and secondar	technical training	technical training	technical training
82	M	Q=P1/population	population	P2	primary and secondar	Technical and vocational education	TVET	TVET
83	M	Q=P1/population	population	P2	primary and secondar	Technical and vocational education	Technical and vocatona	Technical and vocational educatio
84	M	Q=P1/population	population	P2	primary and secondar	Vocational training	Vocational training	Vocational training
85	M	Q=P1/population	population	P2	primary and secondar	young people	young people	young people
86	M	Q=P1/population	population	P2	primary and secondar	youth	youth	youth

Keyword category "O": organisations and initiatives. These are all marked as low priority for the batch and will only be tagged in papers, but not searched							
id	priority	Categories			Code		Lexemes
		category	short	sub-category	semantic value	unique code	English
1	L	Organisations and initiatives	O	Initiative	ALISON	ALISON	ALISON
2	L	Organisations and initiatives	O	Initiative	BRCK	BRCK	BRCK
3	L	Organisations and initiatives	O	Initiative	Bridge	Bridge	Bridge
4	L	Organisations and initiatives	O	organisation	cK-12	cK-12	cK-12
5	L	Organisations and initiatives	O	learning platform	Coursera	Coursera	Coursera
6	L	Organisations and initiatives	O	organisation	Dr Maths	Dr Maths	Dr Maths
7	L	Organisations and initiatives	O	learning platform	edX	edX	edX
8	L	Organisations and initiatives	O	initiative	egyptian teachers first profes	egyptian teacher	egyptian teachers first professional c
9	L	Organisations and initiatives	O	Initiative	EkStep	EkStep	EkStep
10	L	Organisations and initiatives	O	organisation	EMO-Haiti	EMO-Haiti	EMO-Haiti
11	L	Organisations and initiatives	O	Initiative	Eneza	Eneza	Eneza
12	L	Organisations and initiatives	O	initiative	ENLACES	ENLACES	ENLACES
13	L	Organisations and initiatives	O	Initiative	Enuma	Enuma	Enuma
14	L	Organisations and initiatives	O	Initiative	Foundation for Learning Equa	Foundation for Le	Foundation for Learning Equality
15	L	Organisations and initiatives	O	learning platform	Futurelearn	Futurelearn	Futurelearn
16	L	Organisations and initiatives	O	Initiative	Geekie	Geekie	Geekie
17	L	Organisations and initiatives	O	organisation	Hip2BSquared	Hip2BSquared	Hip2BSquared
18	L	Organisations and initiatives	O	Initiative	inABLE	inABLE	inABLE
19	L	Organisations and initiatives	O	initiative	Khan Academy	Khan Academy	Khan Academy
20	L	Organisations and initiatives	O	Organisation	khan academy	khan academy	khan academy
21	L	Organisations and initiatives	O	initiative	KHANYA project	KHANYA project	KHANYA project
22	L	Organisations and initiatives	O	Organisation	kolibri	kolibri	kolibri
23	L	Organisations and initiatives	O	initiative	Lego Project	Lego Project	Lego Project
24	L	Organisations and initiatives	O	Initiative	Mindspark	Mindspark	Mindspark
25	L	Organisations and initiatives	O	learning platform	Mobilearn	Mobilearn	Mobilearn
26	L	Organisations and initiatives	O	initiative	Mxit	Mxit	Mxit
27	L	Organisations and initiatives	O	Initiative	Nafham	Nafham	Nafham

Keyword category "O": organisations and initiatives. These are all marked as low priority for the batch and will only be tagged in papers, but not searched							
id	priority	Categories			Code		Lexemes
		category	short	sub-category	semantic value	unique code	English
28	L	Organisations and initiatives	O	Initiative	OLE	OLE	OLE
29	L	Organisations and initiatives	O	Initiative	one billion	one billion	one billion
30	L	Organisations and initiatives	O	Initiative	One Laptop Per Child	One Laptop Per Child	One Laptop Per Child
31	L	Organisations and initiatives	O	Initiative	Pratham Books' Storyweaver	Pratham Books'	Pratham Books' Storyweaver
32	L	Organisations and initiatives	O	organisation	RETEL	RETEL	RETEL Haiti
33	L	Organisations and initiatives	O	Initiative	Rumie	Rumie	Rumie
34	L	Organisations and initiatives	O	initiative	Scratch	Scratch	Scratch
35	L	Organisations and initiatives	O	Initiative	Siyavula	Siyavula	Siyavula
36	L	Organisations and initiatives	O	initiative	TED	TED	TED
37	L	Organisations and initiatives	O	initiative	the connected learning initiative	the connected le	the connected learning initiative
38	L	Organisations and initiatives	O	initiative	the egyptian knowledge bank	the egyptian kno	the egyptian knowledge bank
39	L	Organisations and initiatives	O	initiative	The global digital library	The global digital	The global digital library
40	L	Organisations and initiatives	O	initiative	the queen rania teacher acad	the queen rania t	the queen rania teacher academy
41	L	Organisations and initiatives	O	Initiative	Ubongo	Ubongo	Ubongo
42	L	Organisations and initiatives	O	learning platform	Udacity	Udacity	Udacity
43	L	Organisations and initiatives	O	Initiative	University of the People	University of the	University of the People
44	L	Organisations and initiatives	O	Initiative	WorldReader	WorldReader	WorldReader
45	L	Organisations and initiatives	O	learning platform	XuetangX	XuetangX	XuetangX
46	L	Organisations and initiatives	O	learning platform	Yoza	Yoza	Yoza

Keyword category "F": Terms relating to the focus of publications. These are all marked as low priority for the batch and will only be tagged in papers, but not search							
id	priority	Categories			Code		Lexemes
		category	short	sub-category	semantic value	unique code	English
1	L	Focus	F	outcomes and im	21st century learning	21st century learning	21st century learning
2	L	Focus	F	outcomes and im	academic achievement	academic achievement	academic achievement
3	L	Focus	F	accessibility and	access	access	access
4	L	Focus	F	accessibility and	access to education	access to education	access to education
5	L	Focus	F	accessibility and	accessibility	accessibility	accessibility
6	L	Focus	F	outcomes and im	Accountability	Accountability	Accountability
7	L	Focus	F	outcomes and im	achievement	achievement	achievement
8	L	Focus	F	outcomes and im	achievement gap	achievement gap	achievement gap
9	L	Focus	F	educational finan	Aid	Aid	Aid
10	L	Focus	F	outcomes and im	assessment	assessment	assessment
11	L	Focus	F	outcomes and im	attainment	attainment	attainment
12	L	Focus	F	learner attitudes	attendance	attendance	attendance
13	L	Focus	F	learner attitudes	attitude	attitude	attitude
14	L	Focus	F	outcomes and im	attribution	attribution	attribution
15	L	Focus	F	educational finan	Bank	Bank	Bank
16	L	Focus	F	educational finan	Banking	Banking	Banking
17	L	Focus	F	learner attitudes	behavior	behavior	behavior
18	L	Focus	F	learner attitudes	behaviour	behaviour	behaviour
19	L	Focus	F	educational finan	Budgeting	Budgeting	Budgeting
20	L	Focus	F	management and	change management	change management	change management
21	L	Focus	F	management and	Charity	Charity	Charity
22	L	Focus	F	management and	Constraints	Constraints	Constraints
23	L	Focus	F	model of delivery	constructivism	constructivism	constructivism
24	L	Focus	F	model of delivery	constructivist	constructivist	constructivist
25	L	Focus	F	educational finan	consumption and capital investment	consumption and capital investment	consumption and capital investment
26	L	Focus	F	educational finan	Cost	Cost	Cost
27	L	Focus	F	educational finan	Cost analysis	Cost analysis	Cost analysis
28	L	Focus	F	educational finan	Cost benefit analysis	Cost benefit analysis	Cost benefit analysis
29	L	Focus	F	educational finan	Cost classification	Cost classification	Cost classification

Keyword category "F": Terms relating to the focus of publications. These are all marked as low priority for the batch and will only be tagged in papers, but not search							
id	priority	Categories			Code		Lexemes
		category	short	sub-category	semantic value	unique code	English
30	L	Focus	F	educational finan	Cost effectiveness	Cost effectiveness	Cost effectiveness
31	L	Focus	F	educational finan	Cost of living	Cost of living	Cost of living
32	L	Focus	F	model of delivery	curricula	curricula	curricula
33	L	Focus	F	model of delivery	curriculum	curriculum	curriculum
34	L	Focus	F	educational finan	Demand	Demand	Demand
35	L	Focus	F	management and	decision-making	decision-making	decision-making
36	L	Focus	F	model of delivery	dialogic pedagogy	dialogic learning	dialogic learning
37	L	Focus	F	model of delivery	dialogic pedagogy	dialogic pedagogy	dialogic pedagogy
38	L	Focus	F	model of delivery	dialogic pedagogy	dialogic teaching	dialogic teaching
39	L	Focus	F	model of delivery	dialogue	dialogue	dialogue
40	L	Focus	F	educational finan	digital economy	digital economy	digital economy
41	L	Focus	F	educational finan	digital goods and services	digital goods and services	digital goods and services
42	L	Focus	F	educational finan	digital trade	digital trade	digital trade
43	L	Focus	F	educational finan	discriminatory taxes	discriminatory taxes	discriminatory taxes
44	L	Focus	F	accessibility and	diversity	diversity	diversity
45	L	Focus	F	accessibility and	divided societies	divided societies	divided societies
46	L	Focus	F	educational finan	Domestic education spending	Domestic education spending	Domestic education spending
47	L	Focus	F	educational finan	Donor	Donor	Donor
48	L	Focus	F	educational finan	donor-sponsored	donor-sponsored	donor-sponsored
49	L	Focus	F	outcomes and im	early literacy	early literacy	early literacy
50	L	Focus	F	educational finan	Economic Factors	Economic Factors	Economic Factors
51	L	Focus	F	educational finan	Economics	Economics	Economics
52	L	Focus	F	educational finan	education financing	education financing	education financing
53	L	Focus	F	educational finan	Education RBF	Education RBF	Education RBF
54	L	Focus	F	educational finan	Education results-based financing	Education results-based financing	Education results-based financing
55	L	Focus	F	accessibility and	educational equality	educational equality	educational equality
56	L	Focus	F	accessibility and	educational equity	educational equity	educational equity
57	L	Focus	F	accessibility and	educational opportunities	educational opportunities	educational opportunities

Keyword category "F": Terms relating to the focus of publications. These are all marked as low priority for the batch and will only be tagged in papers, but not search							
id	priority	Categories			Code		Lexemes
		category	short	sub-category	semantic value	unique code	English
58	L	Focus	F	educational finan	Efficiency	Efficiency	Efficiency
59	L	Focus	F	accessibility and	emancipation	emancipation	emancipation
60	L	Focus	F	accessibility and	empowerment	empowerment	empowerment
61	L	Focus	F	accessibility and	equity	equity	equity
62	L	Focus	F	accessibility and	exclusion	exclusion	exclusion
63	L	Focus	F	educational finan	Expenditures	Expenditures	Expenditures
64	L	Focus	F	educational finan	Expense	Expense	Expense
65		Focus	F	accessibility and	Female	Female	Female
66	L	Focus	F	educational finan	Federal Aid	Federal Aid	Federal Aid
67	L	Focus	F	educational finan	Finance	Finance	Finance
68	L	Focus	F	educational finan	Financers	Financers	Financers
69	L	Focus	F	educational finan	Financial feasibility	Financial feasibility	Financial feasibility
70	L	Focus	F	educational finan	Financial policy	Financial policy	Financial policy
71	L	Focus	F	educational finan	financial stream	financial stream	financial stream
72	L	Focus	F	educational finan	Financial support	Financial support	Financial support
73	L	Focus	F	educational finan	Financing	Financing	Financing
74	L	Focus	F	model of delivery	flexible	flexible	flexible
75	L	Focus	F	educational finan	Fund raising	Fund raising	Fund raising
76	L	Focus	F	educational finan	Funder	Funder	Funder
77	L	Focus	F	educational finan	Funding	Funding	Funding
78	L	Focus	F	educational finan	Funding formula	Funding formula	Funding formula
79	L	Focus	F	educational finan	Funding proposals	Funding proposals	Funding proposals
80	L	Focus	F	educational finan	Fundraising	Fundraising	Fundraising
81	L	Focus	F	accessibility and	gender	gender	gender
82	L	Focus	F	accessibility and	gender equality	gender equality	gender equality
83	L	Focus	F	accessibility and	girl	girl	girl
84	L	Focus	F	management and	government	government	government
85	L	Focus	F	educational finan	Government funding	Government funding	Government funding

Keyword category "F": Terms relating to the focus of publications. These are all marked as low priority for the batch and will only be tagged in papers, but not search							
id	priority	Categories			Code		Lexemes
		category	short	sub-category	semantic value	unique code	English
86	L	Focus	F	management and	Government role	Government role	Government role
87	L	Focus	F	educational finan	high tariffs	high tariffs	high tariffs
88	L	Focus	F	outcomes and im	Improvement	Improvement	Improvement
89	L	Focus	F	learner attitudes	incentives	incentives	incentives
90	L	Focus	F	model of delivery	incidental learning	incidental learning	incidental learning
91	L	Focus	F	accessibility and	inclusion	inclusion	inclusion
92	L	Focus	F	accessibility and	inclusive education	inclusive education	inclusive education
93	L	Focus	F	accessibility and	inclusive learning	inclusive learning	inclusive learning
94	L	Focus	F	model of delivery	information literacy	information literacy	information literacy
95	L	Focus	F	model of delivery	information sciences	information sciences	information sciences
96	L	Focus	F	model of delivery	instructional design	instructional design	instructional design
97	L	Focus	F	model of delivery	instructional innovation	instructional innovation	instructional innovation
98	L	Focus	F	model of delivery	instructionalism	instructionalism	instructionalism
99	L	Focus	F	model of delivery	interactionism	interactionism	interactionism
100	L	Focus	F	model of delivery	interactive	interactive	interactive
101	L	Focus	F	model of delivery	interactive pedagogy	interactive pedagogy	interactive pedagogy
102	L	Focus	F	model of delivery	interactive teaching	interactive teaching	interactive teaching
103	L	Focus	F	model of delivery	intercultural	intercultural	intercultural
104	L	Focus	F	model of delivery	integration	integration	integration
105	L	Focus	F	educational finan	internet economy	internet economy	internet economy
106	L	Focus	F	educational finan	Investments	Investments	Investments
107	L	Focus	F	management and	leadership	leadership	leadership
108	L	Focus	F	outcomes and im	learning	learning	learning
109	L	Focus	F	model of delivery	learning ecologies	learning ecologies	learning ecologies
110	L	Focus	F	model of delivery	life-wide learning	life-wide learning	life-wide learning
111	L	Focus	F	model of delivery	lifelong learning	lifelong learning	lifelong learning
112	L	Focus	F	management and	Limitations	Limitations	Limitations
113	L	Focus	F	outcomes and im	literacy	literacy	literacy

Keyword category "F": Terms relating to the focus of publications. These are all marked as low priority for the batch and will only be tagged in papers, but not search							
id	priority	Categories			Code		Lexemes
		category	short	sub-category	semantic value	unique code	English
114	L	Focus	F	outcomes and im	literacy assessment	literacy assessment	literacy assessment
115	L	Focus	F	management and	management	management	management
116	L	Focus	F	outcomes and im	millennium development goals	MDG	MDG
117	L	Focus	F	outcomes and im	millennium development goals	millennium development goals	millennium development goals
118	L	Focus	F	outcomes and im	media literacy	media literacy	media literacy
119	L	Focus	F	management and	ministry	ministry	ministry
120	L	Focus	F	outcomes and im	monitoring and evaluation	M&E	M&E
121	L	Focus	F	outcomes and im	monitoring and evaluation	monitoring and evaluation	monitoring and evaluation
122	L	Focus	F	outcomes and im	monitoring evaluation and learning	MEL	MEL
123	L	Focus	F	outcomes and im	monitoring evaluation and learning	monitoring evaluation and learning	monitoring evaluation and learning
124	L	Focus	F	learner attitudes	motivation	motivation	motivation
125	L	Focus	F	model of delivery	multilingual education	multilingual education	motivation
126	L	Focus	F	management and	Neo-colonialism	Neo-colonialism	Neo-colonialism
127	L	Focus	F	management and	Neo-liberalism	Neo-liberalism	Neo-liberalism
128	L	Focus	F	management and	Neocolonialism	Neocolonialism	Neocolonialism
129	L	Focus	F	management and	Neoliberalism	Neoliberalism	Neoliberalism
130	L	Focus	F	model of delivery	non-mother-tongue language acquisition	non-mother-tongue language acquisition	non-mother-tongue language acquisition
131	L	Focus	F	outcomes and im	numeracy	numeracy	numeracy
132	L	Focus	F	outcomes and im	numeracy assessment	numeracy assessment	numeracy assessment
133	L	Focus	F	educational finan	Opportunity cost	Opportunity cost	Opportunity cost
134	L	Focus	F	outcomes and im	outcomes	outcomes	outcomes
135	L	Focus	F	educational finan	pay	pay	pay
136	L	Focus	F	educational finan	payment	payment	payment
137	L	Focus	F	model of delivery	pedagogy	pedagogy	pedagogy
138	L	Focus	F	model of delivery	personalised learning	personalised learning	personalised learning
139	L	Focus	F	model of delivery	personalised teaching	personalised teaching	personalised teaching
140	L	Focus	F	educational finan	Philanthropic Foundations	Philanthropic Foundations	Philanthropic Foundations
141	L	Focus	F	management and	policy	policy	policy

Keyword category "F": Terms relating to the focus of publications. These are all marked as low priority for the batch and will only be tagged in papers, but not search							
id	priority	Categories			Code		Lexemes
		category	short	sub-category	semantic value	unique code	English
142	L	Focus	F	educational finan	Private financial support	Private financial support	Private financial support
143	L	Focus	F	management and	Private Public Partnership	PPP	PPP
144	L	Focus	F	management and	Private Public Partnership	Private Public Partnership	Private Public Partnership
145	L	Focus	F	accessibility and	pro-poor	pro-poor	pro-poor
146	L	Focus	F	model of delivery	problem-based learning	PBL	PBL
147	L	Focus	F	model of delivery	problem-based learning	problem-based learning	problem-based learning
148	L	Focus	F	educational finan	Profit	Profit	Profit
149	L	Focus	F	educational finan	Profitability	Profitability	Profitability
150	L	Focus	F	educational finan	Public expenditure on education	Public expenditure on education	Public expenditure on education
151	L	Focus	F	management and	Public relations	Public relations	Public relations
152	L	Focus	F	model of delivery	reading	reading	reading
153	L	Focus	F	management and	regulation	regulation	regulation
154	L	Focus	F	educational finan	remuneration	remuneration	remuneration
155	L	Focus	F	educational finan	Resource Allocation	Resource Allocation	Resource Allocation
156	L	Focus	F	educational finan	Returns	Returns	Returns
157	L	Focus	F	educational finan	Rewards	Rewards	Rewards
158	L	Focus	F	management and	rural	rural	rural
159	L	Focus	F	educational finan	salary	salary	salary
160	L	Focus	F	outcomes and im	scalability	Scalability	Scalability
161	L	Focus	F	educational finan	Scholarships	Scholarships	Scholarships
162	L	Focus	F	management and	School management	School management	School management
163	L	Focus	F	outcomes and im	sustainable development goals	SDG	SDG
164	L	Focus	F	outcomes and im	sustainable development goals	sustainable development goals	sustainable development goals
165	L	Focus	F	management and	service providers	service providers	service providers
166	L	Focus	F	model of delivery	socio-culturalism	socio-culturalism	socio-culturalism
167	L	Focus	F	educational finan	Socioeconomic Status	Socioeconomic Status	Socioeconomic Status
168	L	Focus	F	accessibility and	special needs	special needs	special needs
169	L	Focus	F	outcomes and im	standards	standards	standards

Keyword category "F": Terms relating to the focus of publications. These are all marked as low priority for the batch and will only be tagged in papers, but not search							
id	priority	Categories			Code		Lexemes
		category	short	sub-category	semantic value	unique code	English
170	L	Focus	F	educational finan	State aid	State aid	State aid
171	L	Focus	F	educational finan	Supply	Supply	Supply
172	L	Focus	F	outcomes and im	Sustainability	Sustainability	Sustainability
173	L	Focus	F	educational finan	sustainable revenue streams	sustainable revenue streams	sustainable revenue streams
174	L	Focus	F	management and	systems	systems	systems
175	L	Focus	F	educational finan	taxation regimes	taxation regimes	taxation regimes
176	L	Focus	F	educational finan	Taxes	Taxes	Taxes
177	L	Focus	F	learner attitudes	teacher absenteeism	teacher absenteeism	teacher absenteeism
178	L	Focus	F	learner attitudes	teacher attendance	teacher attendance	teacher attendance
179	L	Focus	F	learner attitudes	teacher identity	teacher identity	teacher identity
180	L	Focus	F	learner attitudes	teacher motivation	teacher motivation	teacher motivation
181	L	Focus	F	model of delivery	teaching approach	teaching approach	teaching approach
182	L	Focus	F	model of delivery	teaching method	teaching method	teaching method
183	L	Focus	F	educational finan	Trade and investment system	Trade and investment system	Trade and investment system
184	L	Focus	F	model of delivery	training needs	training needs	training needs
185	L	Focus	F	model of delivery	training pathway	training pathway	training pathway
186	L	Focus	F	accessibility and	women	women	women
187	L	Focus	F	management and	urban	urban	urban

Keyword category "R": research-methods-related terms. These are all marked as low priority for the batch and will only be tagged in papers, but not searched for.							
id	priority	Categories			Code		Lexemes
		category	short	sub-category	semantic value	unique code	English
1	L	Research methods	R	research methods	action research	action research	action research
2	L	Research methods	R	research method	adaptive	adaptive	adaptive
3	L	Research methods	R	research method	agile	agile	agile
4	L	Research methods	R	research method	anarchy	anarchy	anarchy
5	L	Research methods	R	research method	case study	case study	case study
6	L	Research methods	R	research method	citizen science	citizen science	citizen science
7	L	Research methods	R	research method	correlation	correlation	correlation
8	L	Research methods	R	research method	critical realism	critical realism	critical realism
9	L	Research methods	R	research method	critical theory	critical theory	critical theory
10	L	Research methods	R	research design	design-based implementation re	DBIR	DBIR
11	L	Research methods	R	research design	design-based implementation re	design-based implementation research	design-based implementation research
12	L	Research methods	R	research design	design-based research	DBR	DBR
13	L	Research methods	R	research design	design-based research	design-based research	design-based research
14	L	Research methods	R	research method	deductive	deductive	deductive
15	L	Research methods	R	research method	difference in differences	difference in differences	difference in differences
16	L	Research methods	R	research design	engineering-based research	EBR	EBR
17	L	Research methods	R	research design	engineering-based research	engineering-based research	engineering-based research
18	L	Research methods	R	research method	evaluation	evaluation	evaluation
19	L	Research methods	R	research design	experimental design	experimental design	experimental design
20	L	Research methods	R	research method	focus groups	focus groups	focus groups
21	L	Research methods	R	research method	formative research	formative research	formative research
22	L	Research methods	R	research method	grounded theory	grounded theory	grounded theory
23	L	Research methods	R	research method	group discussions	group discussions	group discussions
24	L	Research methods	R	research method	hermeneutics	hermeneutics	hermeneutics
25	L	Research methods	R	research method	historical	historical	historical
26	L	Research methods	R	research method	impact	impact	impact
27	L	Research methods	R	research method	inductive	inductive	inductive
28	L	Research methods	R	research method	interview	interview	interview
29	L	Research methods	R	research method	iterative	iterative	iterative
30	L	Research methods	R	research method	lean	lean	lean

31	L	Research methods	R	research design	learning analytics	learning analytics	learning analytics
32	L	Research methods	R	research method	literature analysis	literature analysis	literature analysis
33	L	Research methods	R	research method	literature review	literature review	literature review
34	L	Research methods	R	research method	long interview	long interview	long interview
35	L	Research methods	R	research method	meta-analysis	meta-analysis	meta-analysis
36	L	Research methods	R	research design	mixed method	mixed method	mixed method
37	L	Research methods	R	research method	modelling	modelling	modelling
38	L	Research methods	R	research method	observation	observation	observation
39	L	Research methods	R	research method	participatory video	participatory video	participatory video
40	L	Research methods	R	research method	positivist	positivist	positivist
41	L	Research methods	R	research design	quasi-experimental design	QED	QED
42	L	Research methods	R	research design	quasi-experimental design	quasi-experimental design	quasi-experimental design
43	L	Research methods	R	research method	qualitative	qualitative	qualitative
44	L	Research methods	R	research method	quantitative	quantitative	quantitative
45	L	Research methods	R	research method	questionnaire	questionnaire	questionnaire
46	L	Research methods	R	research design	randomised control trial	randomised control trial	randomised control trial
47	L	Research methods	R	research design	randomised control trial	RCT	RCT
48	L	Research methods	R	research method	regression	regression	regression
49	L	Research methods	R	research design	regression discontinuity design	regression discontinuity design	regression discontinuity design
50	L	Research methods	R	research design	research design	research design	research design
51	L	Research methods	R	research method	research method	research method	research method
52	L	Research methods	R	research method	rich text analysis	rich text analysis	rich text analysis
53	L	Research methods	R	research method	semi-structured interview	semi-structured interview	semi-structured interview
54	L	Research methods	R	research method	structured interview	structured interview	structured interview
55	L	Research methods	R	research method	survey	survey	survey
56	L	Research methods	R	research method	synthesis	synthesis	synthesis
57	L	Research methods	R	research method	systematic review	systematic review	systematic review
58	L	Research methods	R	research method	tracer study	tracer study	tracer study
59	L	Research methods	R	research method	trial	trial	trial
60	L	Research methods	R	research method	unstructured interview	unstructured interview	unstructured interview
61	L	Research methods	R	research method	usability	usability	usability
62	L	Research methods	R	research method	video	video	video
63	L	Research methods	R	research method	program evaluation	program evaluation	program evaluation
64	L	Research methods	R	research method	programme evaluation	programme evaluation	programme evaluation

65	L	Research methods	R	research method	randomised control trial	randomised control trials	randomised control trials
66	L	Research methods	R	research method	randomised control trial	randomized control trial	randomized control trial
67	L	Research methods	R	research method	randomised control trial	randomized controlled trial	randomized controlled trial
68	L	Research methods	R	research method	randomised control trial	randomized controlled trials	randomized controlled trials
69	L	Research methods	R	research method	quasi-experimental design	field experiment	field experiment
70	L	Research methods	R	research method	quasi-experimental design	randomly sampled	randomly sampled
71	L	Research methods	R	research method	quasi-experimental design	representative sample	representative sample
72	L	Research methods	R	research method	mixed method	mixed methods	mixed methods
73	L	Research methods	R	research method	mixed method	mixed-method	mixed-method
74	L	Research methods	R	research method	mixed method	mixed-methods	mixed-methods
75	L	Research methods	R	research method	mixed method	Multiple research approach	Multiple research approach
76	L	Research methods	R	research method	mixed method	Multimethod	Multimethod
77	L	Research methods	R	research method	mixed method	multimethodology	multimethodology
78	L	Research methods	R	research method	mixed method	combined research	combined research
79	L	Research methods	R	research method	mixed method	triangulation	triangulation
80	L	Research methods	R	research method	mixed method	triangulate	triangulate
81	L	Research methods	R	research method	mixed method	multi-method	multi-method
82	L	Research methods	R	research method	mixed method	complement	complement
83	L	Research methods	R	research method	mixed method	complementarity	complementarity
84	L	Research methods	R	research method	mixed method	mixed analysis	mixed analysis
85	L	Research methods	R	research method	mixed method	mixed research	mixed research
86	L	Research methods	R	research method	mixed method	hybrid methods	hybrid methods
87	L	Research methods	R	research method	mixed method	construct research	construct research
88	L	Research methods	R	research method	mixed method	integrated research	integrated research
89	L	Research methods	R	research method	research design	study design	study design
90	L	Research methods	R	research method	research design	project design	project design
91	L	Research methods	R	research method	research method	research methodology	research methodology
92	L	Research methods	R	research method	research method	research methods	research methods
93	L	Research methods	R	research method	research method	research approach	research approach